

THE CONCEPT OF COMMUNICATION AND ITS MAIN TYPES

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Abstract

This article will talk about the concept of communication and its main types. Reasoned opinion and reasoning were used throughout the article. The article was last mentioned giving conclusions and suggestions.

Keywords

types of communication, personality thinking, images and models, the concept of communication.

Communication is an important condition for human life and activity. It is with the help of communication that human beings have the opportunity to assimilate their nature and act together to meet their individual needs. In the process of communication, certain images and models of human behavior are formed, which then enter into a person. The thinking of a person, the ability to analyze and evaluate the universe and his image are formed in the process of communication.

The Polish psychologist Ye, who gave a thorough assessment of this problem. Melibruda notes: "communication is as important in interpersonal relationships as we are in the air."

Since communication is an extremely complex process, it is very difficult to give it the only correct definition. Therefore, usually the content of the concept of communication is defined by emphasizing certain aspects of it.

1) communication is the process of establishing and developing communication, which is dictated by the need for collaborative activities.

2) communication - interaction of subjects through a system of signs.

A.V. In the textbook "general psychology", which came out under Petrovsky's edit, communication is recognized as a process consisting of information separation, interaction and mutual understanding between two and more people.

M.G. The textbook "General Psychology", published under the authorship of Davletshin, states that communication is an interaction between two or more

people that consists in the affective evaluative character and the exchange of information on cognition".

M.G. In the concise Explanatory Dictionary "Psychology", published under Davletshin's guidance, communication is defined as: communication is the interaction of two or more people.

E.G'. Communication in the educational manual "Social Psychology", published in the authorship of goziev, is a process that depends on the need for entrepreneurial activity, helping in the development of interpersonal relationships.

In accordance with the above definitions, communication can be defined in a general way as follows: communication is the process of interaction of at least two people, during which information is exchanged, attitudes are established, developed.

The concept of communication should be distinguished from the concept of communication. Communication refers to the exchange of information between systems of a living and dead nature. The exchange of signals between animals, the fact that humanity communicates with technical means, all this is an example of communication.

Communication can only be done between humans. The importance of communication in a person's life is incomparable. A human child becomes a person precisely in communication with others, in the process of relationships. Through communication, a person acquires social experience and culture. When a newborn person is deprived of the opportunity to interact with others, he will never be able to become a person, that is, he will lag behind in his own psychic progress. After all, human psychic development begins with communication.

Without communication, there can be no human society. It is the dialogue that forms the community of individuals that operate cooperatively. Dialogue between the individuals to create a collaborative activity plan and bring it to fruition

must be implemented. Through communication, collaborative activities are organized and carried out. At the same time, during the activity, new-new relationships and communication between people are formed. Hence, communication and activity are closely related.

We can clearly see in the following examples how high importance communication is in a person's life:

Example 1. 1938 Richard Bard willingly remain secluded for 6 months in the glaciers of Antarctica. On the one hand, he was interested in the results of the experiment, and on the other, he wanted to relax a little from the hustle and bustle of everyday life. He would later recollect this period with the words "throughout

my life here my every effort, every work, was becoming increasingly meaningless, illogical, aimless. Although I am a person who is not afraid of dangers, for some reason I began to risk that the roof was overrun here. In my diet, regularity disappeared, I did not wash."

Example 2. Historically, the Japanese had a human self-improvement system called "Moritao". However, a person does not suffer any physical suffering. Only for a week does he go into a cave, where he remains secluded. Here he could not even speak to himself. Those who pass the test will then cheerfully confront any meeting and conversation. It is interesting that they do not have the need to talk more, but as the need to listen increases.

Example 3. At one time, automation of all tobacco shops was in full swing in America. But soon their owners began to meet kasod. It turns out that people came here not only to Tammy, but also to find an interlocutor.

It can be seen from this that humans constantly need communication and try to satisfy it.

Communication functions also play an important role in the communication process. Communication functions (functions) are understood as the functions that communication performs in a person's life. Communication functions are diverse, and according to the most common classification, i.e. B.F. Proposed by Lomov, it consists of.

-Informational - communicative function-the task of ensuring the exchange of information. Information exchange is carried out through various character systems. Usually verbal and nonverbal communication are distinguished.

- Regulation-communicative function-the task of ensuring the regularization of the behavior of interlocutors. In the process of communication, individuals can influence each other's motives, goals, decision-making in verbal ways, motivate and control their movement, influence each other's behavior in a stimulating and corrective way.

- The function of Affective-communicative is the task of ensuring the regularization of the human emotional sphere. Communication is the most important determinacy of the human emotional state. Because different emotional states arise and change in the process of communication.

L.A. According to the classification proposed by Karpenko, the following tasks of communication are distinguished.

- The task of establishing communication-to get the interlocutor to enter the aioca preparation;

- Informational task-exchange of certain information, thoughts and plans with the interlocutor;
- Motivation to activity-stimulation of the sufferer to perform an action;
- Coordination task-organization of collaborative activities with the interlocutor and coordination of actions in its implementation;
- The task of ensuring understanding is to understand the thoughts and feelings of the interlocutor;
- Amotiv task-to awaken a certain emotion in the interlocutor and change them;
- Establishing a relationship-determining the personal position, position in the relationship system;
- Influence-change the goals and masters of personal characteristics of the interlocutor's behavior.

Communicative aspect of communication

During the joint activity, people share various thoughts, thoughts, experiences. In this case, mind-flkrs, emotions can be interpreted as information, and communication as information exchange. But it should be noted that interpersonal communication does not consist simply of information exchanges. Because in the process of communication, information is not only transmitted, but also formed, clarified, developed. Therefore, it is impossible for a person to consider communication as a process consisting simply of the exchange of information.

After all, in the process of communication from the first, information is not simply moved from one side to the other, but is actively exchanged (participants in the communicative process analyze each other's motives, goals, workshops, etc.);

- secondly, in the process of communication, those who exchange information can influence each other through signs (in the exchange of interpersonal information, of course, a certain influence is exerted on the interlocutor's behavior);

- third in the process of communication, the communicator (the person sending information) and the opponent (the person receiving information) must have the same coding system;

- fourth in the process of communication, only barriers characteristic of interpersonal communication can occur.

There are several character systems that can be used in the communicative process. They are verbal communication (through speech) and nonverbal (through non-speech-related characters) communication.

Verbal communication. Human speech is used as a system of signs. Speech-consists of sound signals or written signs used by a person, through which

information from communication is processed, stored and transmitted. It is carried out through the process language. Language is a system of verbal signs, which occurs as a product of psychic activity in the process of communication.

Language is a means of dealing. Language provides communication between those who enter into circulation, since it is understood by both the informant and the recipient alike. The informant (communicator) and the recipient (recipient) to another person must use the same language in the communication process, otherwise they will not be able to understand each other correctly.

The exchange of information should have an understandable character and content to the participants in the treatment. Language consists of the sum of word symbols. The meaning of the word is its content side. 3 important factors belie E the actions and activities of each individual person and the actions and activities of another person.

First, it defines the socio-historical experience of all mankind or a community of people of some narrow circle. A small child will not know the world independently. She asks her parents questions and they answer her. From these answers, the child learns only a small part of the general knowledge that he uses his activity later.

Only this small part of general knowledge can be generated by the child in the form of a language, in the system of word symbols using a language. The school will do the same. The student absorbs all knowledge about the universe from the teacher's explanation or textbook, that is, with the help of language. Here language is manifested in the way that it fulfills one of its important functions, that is, the means of living, the means of giving and mastering socio-historical experience.

Secondly, the work and activities of each individual person often determine the direct experiences of other people who do not have social value. For example, I go to the kitchen. On the way, my comrade meets and tells me: "the kitchen is closed." At this time, this message manages my activities in a certain way: I turn around and leave for another kitchen. Here, Language manifests itself with its other important function, either as a tool or a method of communication, or as a tool that controls the behavior of the universe. The result is any communication, any relationship consists in influencing the interlocutor.

Thirdly, the work-actions and activities of each individual person are determined by the personal experience of each individual person. A person's "personal" own individual experience consists of a specific mixture of other people's experiences and social experience. A person, unlike an animal, can plan his actions. The main weapon for solving such planning and general opinion issues is

language. Here we are faced with the task of the third task of language as a weapon of mental activity (perception, memory, thinking, imagination). As a system of verbal signs, the language is used in speech activities.

Speech activity is the process of mastering the socio-historical experience by a person and giving it to descendants or establishing communication, using language in order to plan their actions. Language is a means of communication or a weapon, and speech activity or speech is the process of communication itself. In this process, active and passive types of speech activity are distinguished.

The speaker's speech is active speech, the listener's speech is passive speech. Speech is divided into internal and external speech.

External speech-divided into written and oral speech, and oral speech-into monologue and dialogical speech. A monologue is a speech of one person aimed at himself or others. This is the teacher's statement, the student's fuller answer, a lecture, etc. Monological speech has certain difficulties. The person speaking in the monologue should pay attention to the accuracy of thoughts, the preservation of grammatical rules, logic and the consistency of what is being said.

In relation to dialogical speech, monological speech is formed later. At school, teachers should pay special attention to the development of monological speech in students. Speech in two or more kishiiar Scrolls is called dialogue. In dialogical speech, the thought being expressed will largely depend on the opinion before it. In dialogical speech, certain words known to the interlocutors are dropped. Therefore, the recorded dialogue may not be very understandable to others: in dialogical speech, templates of various types, that is, combinations of words that are used to, are common (bold, say with Blessing).

The so-called internal speech is a special type of speech activity. Internal speech manifests itself as a planning phase of practical and theoretical activities. We will understand as soon as we play the word-half. Internal speech can occur earlier than certain acts of oral speech, in particular earlier than oral speech, where the level of volatility is much higher.

Written speech is one of the types of monological speech, and written speech is more detailed than monological speech.

Also, the American journalist C. Lassuel offers a model of a communicative process consisting of five elements.

Who (information is transmitted by whom)

What (what information is transmitted)

How (in what way is information transmitted)

To whom (to whom information is directed)

How effective (how effective the information was transmitted) □

The communicative process can be either axial (in which information is directed to some specific people) or retial (in which information is directed to a number of possible opponents) in nature.

In the communicative process, it is very important for the initiators of mutual tnuosabat to understand each other. In this, the following important features of speech appear, namely content, intelligibility, expressiveness, impressiveness.

The great French writer Antoine Saint Exupéry wrote that "communication is such a boon through which man is delighted".

Regarding the nature of the word, Saadi said, "You Are Smart or stupid, you are big or small, we cannot know this until you say a word."

In our people there is such an instructive phrase "human intelligence is manifested in the clarity of his speech."

Tools of nonverbal communication-facial expression, facial expressions, tone, Pause, pose (posture), tears, laughter, etc. These tools complement, reinforce, and sometimes replace verbal communication - the word. Bulgarians do not have no head shaking means that the Russians will have the opposite. In different age groups, the means of nonverbal communication vary. For example, children often use crying as a means of influencing adults, giving them their own desires and moods. The correspondence of nonverbal means of communication to the content and purpose of the verbal statement of information is a kind of culture of treatment.

Nonverbal communication includes the optical-kinetic system of characters, which includes gestures (arm 1 movement), facial expressions (facial movements), and pantomimics (arm 1, leg, body movement).

Gestures are hand movements of a person, through which the inner state of a person, his attitude to some object and orientation to the outer world are expressed. In one people or another, gestures are perceived differently. The Italian and French cannot reciprocate their dialogue without gestures. In the Uzbek people, the use of gestures in speech is not perceived as a good habit. But it should also be noted that nonverbal communication makes it possible to express thoughts that have ceased to be expressed in oral speech.

Mimicry is a part of human facial movements through which a person is manifested in thoughts, behavior, imagination, memory, surprise, etc.

Pantomimics is a system of actions expressed using the human body or its parts. Studies show that in the process of everyday communication, words make

up 7%, sounds and intonation make up 38%, and non-speech communication makes up 55%.

As the publicist said, we "speak with The Voice, talk with the body." Let's consider another system of signs of nonverbal communication.

The paralinguistic and extralinguistic sign system is a system of localization, which manifests its diaposon as a voice in the pace of pauses in speech, cough, crying, laughter, speech.

It is also important in the process of communication that the initiators of communication are positioned in relation to each other. For example, the placement of tables in the auditorium is very inconvenient for communication. Especially in the process of seminar classes, the teacher, the rest during the speaker's dialogue, does not have the opportunity to actively participate in the discussion.

It is also useful to hold seminars, or a similar conversation, on table chairs arranged in the form of a "T", but communication on a round-shaped recessed table, chairs is very effective.

In visual communication, the "eye contact" character system is also used. This system is important in the work activities of educators, leaders.

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